

AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS OF PMR POLYIMIDE COMPOSITES

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Summary

Advanced fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites are achieving acceptance as engineering materials for the design and fabrication of high performance aerospace structural components. Epoxy resins are the most widely-used polymer matrix materials because of their excellent mechanical properties and processing characteristics. A disadvantage of epoxy resins is that their upper-use temperature is limited to approximately 175°C. Until recently, the intractable nature of higher temperature resistant polymers, which in theory could provide nearly a two-fold increase in use-temperature, has prevented the realization of the full potential of these polymers as matrix resins for high-temperature polymer matrix composites.

The novel class of processable, addition-type polyimides known as PMR (for in situ polymerization of monomer reactants) polyimides was developed by investigators at the NASA Lewis Research Center. Because the final cure of PMR polyimides occurs without the release of volatile materials, high quality void-free composites can be fabricated by either compression or autoclave molding techniques.

The purpose of this paper is to review the current status of PMR polyimides. Emphasis is given to reviewing the aerospace applications of PMR-15 polyimide composites.

Introduction

In the early 1970's after nearly two decades of hope and promise, but delivering little more, high-temperature polymer matrix composites appeared to be destined to forever remaining laboratory curiosities. In marked contrast, low-temperature polymer matrix composites based on epoxy matrix resins were becoming accepted as engineering materials for the design and fabrication of high performance structural components. Although high-temperature polymer matrix composites provided an opportunity to achieve nearly a two-fold increase in use-temperature compared to fiber reinforced epoxies, the intractable nature of early technology high-temperature polymers made it impossible to fabricate defect-free structural components. The presence of these defects, or voids, seriously degraded composite mechanical properties and thermo-oxidative stability.

In response to the need for high-temperature polymers with improved processability, investigators at the NASA Lewis Research Center developed the novel class of addition-type polyimides known as PMR (for in situ polymerization of monomer reactants) polyimides (1-3). The PMR concept consists of impregnating the reinforcing fibers with a monomer mixture dissolved in a low boiling point alkyl alcohol. The monomers are essentially unreactive at room temperature, but undergo sequential in situ condensation and ring-opening addition crosslinking reactions at elevated temperatures to form a thermo-oxidatively stable polyimide matrix resin. Because the final in situ reaction occurs without the release of volatile materials, high quality void-free composites can be fabricated by either compression or autoclave molding techniques. Thus, the highly processable PMR polyimides have made it possible to realize much of the potential of high-temperature polymer matrix composites.

Studies conducted at NASA Lewis have identified monomer reactant combinations for several PMR polyimides differing in chemical composition. The earliest, or "first generation," PMR resin is designated PMR-15. Unidirectional and bidirectional fiber prepreg materials and chopped fiber molding compounds employing PMR-15 are commercially available from the major suppliers of composite materials.

The purpose of this paper is to review the current status of PMR polyimides. Highlights of PMR technology studies conducted at NASA Lewis are presented. Several examples of industrial application of PMR-15 polyimide composites to aerospace structural components are also presented.

PMR Polyimide Technology

Most organic polymers soften or melt below 204°C or begin to decompose at temperatures slightly above 204°C. High-temperature polymers can be defined as those organic polymers which can withstand continuous exposure in air at temperatures as high as 316°C, and still maintain useful mechanical properties during or after exposure. The key to preparing high-temperature polymers is to incorporate highly stable structural units in the polymer chain, such as aromatic rings and/or heterocyclic rings. These structural units are able to absorb thermal energy and contain a minimum of oxidizable hydrogen atoms. Although high-temperature polymers degrade during exposure at elevated temperatures, they degrade at a very slow rate, and they degrade into thermally stable residues which retain structural integrity.

Numerous polymers have been synthesized which are thermo-oxidatively stable at or above 316°C. In addition to being resistant to elevated temperatures, these polymers are also resistant to being processed into useful structural components. The molecular structural units that are responsible

for the thermal stability of high-temperature polymers are also responsible for their inherent insolubility and infusibility, commonly referred to as intractability.

In the early 1970's the most highly developed high-temperature polymers, and those that had achieved commercial status were the condensation-type, aryl polyimides. Aryl polyimides are generally prepared in a two step reaction by reacting aromatic diamines with aromatic dianhydrides, with aromatic tetracarboxylic acids, or with dialkyl esters of aromatic tetracarboxylic acids. The diamine-dianhydride reaction is preferred for preparing films and coatings, whereas the latter two combinations of reactants are generally employed for the preparation of matrix resins. Prepreg solutions are prepared by dissolving the appropriate reactants in high boiling point aprotic solvents, or in solvent mixtures containing an aprotic solvent. The amide-acid prepolymer that forms in the first step of the reaction remains soluble. In the second step, which occurs readily, water is eliminated (condensation reaction) as the thermally stable imide ring is formed. Perhaps the significance of these reactions can be more fully appreciated with reference to a commonly used composites fabrication process, namely compression molding. If excessive ring closure occurs as heat is applied to effect removal of prepreg solvent and reaction by-products during the course of a fabrication process involving the use of condensation-type polyimides, the prepreg becomes intractable. In an attempt to avoid this occurrence, complicated time/temperature/pressure cure schedules are utilized to achieve removal of the solvent and reaction by-products and still maintain sufficient fusibility. Unfortunately, some residual solvent, reaction by-products, and even air are trapped, particularly in laminates having a thickness greater than 40 mils, resulting in voids. The deleterious effect of voids on mechanical properties and thermo-oxidative stability is well-known.

The PMR approach was developed to circumvent the shortcomings associated with condensation-type polyimides. Figure 1 outlines some salient features of the PMR polyimide approach for the fabrication of composites. In the PMR approach, the reinforcing fibers are hot-melt or solution impregnated with a

Figure 1. - NASA Lewis PMR polyimide technology.

monomer reactant mixture dissolved in a low-boiling-point alkyl alcohol, such as methanol or ethanol. The monomer reactant mixture contains a dialkyl ester of an aromatic tetracarboxylic acid, an aromatic diamine, and a mono-alkyl ester of 5-norbornene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (NE). The number of moles of each reactant is governed by the following ratio:

$$n:(n+1):2$$

Where n , $(n+1)$, and 2 are the number of moles of the dialkyl ester of the aromatic tetracarboxylic acid, the aromatic diamine, and NE, respectively. In situ polymerization of the monomer reactants (PMR) occurs when the impregnated fibers are heated. A condensation reaction forming low molecular weight norbornenyl-encapped oligomers occurs in the temperature range of 121°-232°C. At temperatures in the range of 275°-350°C, the norbornenyl groups undergo a ring-opening reaction generating maleic chain ends and cyclopentadiene. The maleic functions immediately copolymerize with the cyclopentadiene and unreacted norbornenyl groups to form a crosslinked polyimide without the evolution of undesirable volatile materials.

In the initial study (1) which established the feasibility of the PMR approach, it was noted that composites made from monomer solutions containing the dimethyl ester of 3,3',4,4'-benzophenonetetracarboxylic acid (BTDE), 4,4'-methylenedianiline (MDA) and NE exhibited a higher level of thermo-oxidative stability than did composites prepared from a monomer solution consisting of the dimethyl ester of pyromellitic acid, MDA and NE. This unexpected observation was confirmed in a subsequent study (4), and the optimum number of moles of BTDE (n) which provided the best overall balance of processing characteristics and thermo-oxidative stability was found to be 2.087, corresponding to a PMR polyimide having a formulated molecular weight (FMW) of 1500. The FMW is considered to be the average molecular weight of imidized prepolymer that could have been formed if an amide-acid prepolymer had been synthesized. The equation for the FMW of a PMR polyimide prepared from n moles of BTDE, $(n+1)$ moles of MDA and 2 moles of NE is:

$$FMW = n MW_{BTDE} + (n+1) MW_{MDA} + 2 MW_{NE} - 2 (n+1) [MW_{H_2O} + MW_{CH_3OH}]$$

Where MW_{BTDE} , MW_{MDA} , etc., are the molecular weights of the monomer reactants and by-products. It is now common practice to denote the stoichiometry of a PMR resin by dividing the FMW by 100. PMR matrices employing BTDE are referred to as "first generation" materials. The first generation PMR Matrix prepared by BTDE, MDA and NE having an FMW of 1500 is widely known as PMR-15. Prepreg materials based on PMR-15 are commercially available in the U.S.A. from the major prepreg suppliers. The structures of the monomers used in PMR-15 are shown in Table I.

These early studies (1,4) also clearly demonstrated the efficacy and versatility of the PMR approach. By varying the chemical nature of either the dialkyl ester acid or aromatic diamine, or both, and the monomer reactant stoichiometry, PMR matrices having a broad range of processing characteristics and properties could easily be synthesized. A modified PMR-15, called LARC-160, has been developed by substituting an aromatic polyamine for MDA (5). Other studies (6) have shown that the PMR approach has excellent potential for "tailor making" matrix resins with specific properties. Figure 2 shows the effect of FMW on resin flow for PMR-HTS graphite fiber composites. It can be seen that significantly higher resin flow can be achieved by reducing the FMW. However, the PMR compositions which exhibited increased resin flow were found to be less thermo-oxidatively stable at 288°C. The lower resin flow and increased thermo-oxidative stability in going from PMR-10 to PMR-15 clearly show the sensitivity of these properties to imide

Table I. - Monomers used for PMR-15.

STRUCTURE	NAME	ABBREVIATION
	MONOMETHYL ESTER OF 5-NORBORNENE-2,3-DICARBOXYLIC ACID	NE
	DIMETHYL ESTER OF 3,3',4,4'-BENZOPHENONETETRACARBOXYLIC ACID	BTDE
	4,4'-METHYLENEDIANILINE	MDA

CS-71803

Figure 2. - Resin flow of HTS graphite/PMR composites. (Resin flow is based on weight of resin flash during molding).

ring and alicyclic contents. The reduction in resin flow with increased FMW also serves to qualitatively account for the intractable nature of linear, high-molecular-weight condensation polyimides.

The thermo-oxidative stability of PMR-15 is far in excess of what would be predicted on the basis of its molecular structure versus the generally accepted polymer-molecular-structural criteria for polymer thermo-oxidative stability. For example, the alicyclic content of PMR-15 is about 12.3 percent by weight. This high level of non-heteroaromatic structure should render the polymer useless for long term service in air at elevated temperatures. In a study (7) to correlate the stability of the individual components in PMR-15 with the composite weight loss during 316°C exposure in air, it was found that the stability of the monomer reactants decreased in the following order:

BTDE > NE >> MDA

After 1200 to 1500 hours of exposure, the NE crosslinker exhibited a marked increase in degradation which correlates with the 316°C performance of PMR-15 composites.

Replacement of BTDE with the dimethyl ester of 4,4'-(hexafluoroisopropylidene)-bis(phthalic acid) (HFDE) significantly improved the thermo-oxidative stability of "first generation" PMR resins (8). However, the initial 316°C mechanical properties of HFDE/MDA/NE PMR polyimide composites were considerably lower than the corresponding properties of BTDE/MDA/NE PMR polyimides. Graphite fiber reinforced PMR polyimide composites prepared from a monomer solution consisting of HFDE, p-Phenylenediamine and NE at an FMW of 1267 (n=1.67) were found to exhibit significantly improved thermo-oxidative stability and retention of mechanical properties at 316°C compared to PMR-15 composites (9). The HFDE-PMR compositions are referred to as "second generation" materials to differentiate them from the "first generation" BTDE-PMR materials. The "second generation" resin consisting of HFDE, PPDA and NE with n=1.67, is known as PMR II. Second generation PMR prepreg materials are not commercially available because a commercial source for the di-anhydride of HFDE is non-existent.

As described earlier, current technology PMR-15 polyimide prepreg solutions are generally prepared by dissolving the monomer mixture in a low-boiling-point alkyl alcohol. Although the volatility of these solvents is highly desirable for obtaining void-free composites, it does limit the tack and drape retention characteristics of unprotected prepreg exposed to the ambient. PMR-15 monomer reactants and a mixed solvent have been identified which provide prepreg materials with improved tack and drape retention characteristics without changing the basic cure chemistry, processability, or thermo-oxidative stability (10). The modifications consist of substituting higher alkyl esters for the methyl esters in NE and BTDE and using a solvent mixture (3:1 methanol/1-propanol) in lieu of pure methanol. The higher tack version is designated PMR-15 IT. The solvent and ester modifications extended the tack retention to beyond 12 days under ambient exposure conditions.

High pressure (compression) and low pressure (autoclave) molding cycles have been developed for fabrication of fiber reinforced PMR composites. Although the thermally-induced, addition-cure reaction of the norbornenyl group occurs at temperatures in the range of 275° to 350°C, nearly all of the processes developed use a maximum cure temperature of 316°C. Cure times of 1 to 2 hours followed by a free standing postcure in air at 316°C for 4 to 16 hours are also normally employed. Compression molding cycles generally

employ high rates of heating (5 to 10°C/min) and pressures in the range of 3.45×10 to 6.0×10 N/m. Vacuum bag autoclave processes at low heating rates (2 to 4°C/min) and pressures of 1.38×10 N/m or less have been successfully used to fabricate void-free composites. The successful application of autoclave processing methodology to PMR polyimides results from the presence of a thermal transition, termed "melt-flow", which occurs over a fairly broad temperature range (11). The lower limit of the melt-flow temperature range depends on a number of factors including the chemical nature and stoichiometry of the monomer reactant mixture, and the prior thermal history of the PMR prepreg.

Differential scanning calorimetry studies have shown the presence of four thermal transitions which occur during the overall cure of a PMR polyimide (12). The first, second, and third transitions are endothermic and are related to the following: (1) melting of the monomer reactant mixture below 100°C, (2) in situ reaction of the monomers at 140°C, and (3) melting of the norbornenyl terminated prepolymers at the range of 175°C to 250°C, referred to as the melt-flow temperature range. The fourth transition, centered near 340°C, is exothermic and is related to the addition-crosslinking reaction. To a large extent the excellent processing characteristics of PMR polyimides can be attributed to the presence of these widely separated and chemically distinct thermal transitions. During the first and second thermal transitions solvent and condensation by-products are volatilized without converting the polymer into an intractable state. During the third thermal transition, and with the application of pressure, fusion occurs. At still higher temperatures, and while maintaining the applied pressure, the addition-cure reaction occurs. The high-temperature postcure mentioned earlier must be used to obtain optimum thermo-oxidative stability and mechanical properties retention at elevated temperatures.

The cure temperature requirements of both first and second generation PMR polyimides exceed the capabilities of many existing autoclave facilities and impose a severe strain on the temperature capabilities of current bagging and sealant materials. By replacing the norbornenyl endcaps with m-aminostyrene, the final cure temperature was lowered to 260°C (13). However, the glass transition temperature (T_g) of this PMR polyimide, even after postcure, ranged between 270°C to 280°C, thus limiting their upper use-temperature to about 260°C. A subsequent study (14) showed that by replacing 50 mole percent of NE with p-aminostyrene (PAS) the final cure temperature could be reduced to 232°C without sacrificing 316°C thermo-oxidative stability. Because this modification resulted in reduced resin flow, a molding pressure of 8.27 MPa was required to obtain defect-free laminates. The addition of low levels, 4 and 9 mole percent, of a fourth monomer reactant, a mono-functional norbornenyl crosslinker (PN), to PMR-15 increased its resin flow and 316°C thermo-oxidative stability (15). An undesirable effect of PN addition was a reduction in T_g .

Many investigations have been conducted to determine the effects of various hostile environments on the physical and mechanical properties of PMR-15 composites. Glass (16), graphite (17-19), and Kevlar (20) composites have been studied. Figure 3 shows the excellent 316°C interlaminar strength retention characteristics of PMR-15 composites made with four different graphite fibers (18). The difference in strength levels between the Celanese Celion 6000 composites and the other composites was attributed to differences in fiber surface morphologies. Scanning electron microscopy analysis showed that the surface of the Hercules HTS-2, Great Lakes Fortafil 3, and Union Carbide Thornel B graphite fibers was considerably smoother than the Celion 6000 surface.

Figure 3. - Interlaminar shear strength of graphite fiber/PMR-15 composites

Although we, and others, have identified and investigated many modified versions of PMR-15, the composition of the resin employed for commercial products is essentially unchanged from the original composition identified and developed at NASA Lewis in the early to mid-seventies.

Structural Applications of PMR-15 Polyimide Composites

Fiber reinforced/PMR-15 polyimide composites are finding increased acceptance as engineering materials for the design and fabrication of aerospace structural components, particularly aeropropulsion structural components. A variety of structural components is being fabricated, ranging from small compression molded bearings to large autoclave molded aircraft engine cowls and ducts. Processing technology and baseline materials data are also being developed for the application of PMR-15 composites in weapon systems. Firms involved in the manufacture of small compression molded bearings, made from particulate or chopped fiber PMR molding compounds, have found it convenient to become captive producers of PMR-15 resin. In contrast, firms involved in the fabrication of larger components, made from tape or fabric materials, rely on traditional sources of composite materials for PMR-15 prepreg.

Some representative applications of PMR-15 composites are listed in Table II. A brief discussion of each of the components listed in Table II follows.

The blade illustrated in Figure 4 was the first structural component fabricated with a PMR-15 composite material. The reinforcement is HTS graphite fiber. The blade design was conceived by Pratt and Whitney Aircraft

CS-73471

Figure 4. - Graphite fiber/PMR-15 polyimide fan blade (span, chord, and maximum thickness = 28,20,and 1.3 cm, respectively).

Table II. - Applications of PMR-15 composites

Component	Agency	Contractor
Ultra-high tip speed fan blades	NASA LeRC	PWA/TRW
QCSEE inner cowl	NASA LeRC	GE
F404 outer duct	Navy/NASA LeRC	GE
F110 inner duct	Air Force	GE
T700 swirl frame	Army	GE
JT8D reverser stang fairing	NASA LeRC	McDonnell-Douglas
Shuttle orbiter aft body flap	NASA LeRC	Boeing
Ion thruster beam shield	NASA LeRC	Hughes

for an ultra-high-speed fan stage (21). Blade tooling and fabrication were performed by TRW Equipment (22). The blade span is 28 cm and the chord is 20 cm. The blade thickness ranges from about 1.3 cm just above the midpoint of the wedge shaped root to 0.06 cm at the leading edge. At its thickest section the composite structure consists of 77 plies of material arranged in varying fiber orientation. The "line of demarkation" visible in Figure 4 at approximately one-third the blade-span from the blade-tip resulted from a required change in fiber orientation from 40 degrees in the lower region to 75 degrees in the upper region to meet torsional stiffness requirements. Ultrasonic and radiographic examination of the compression molded blades indicated that they were defect free. Although some minor internal defects were induced in the blade during low cycle and high cycle fatigue testing, the successful fabrication of these highly complex blades established the credibility of PMR-15 as a processable matrix resin.

Figure 5 shows the inner cowl installed on an experimental engine, called QCSEE for a Quiet Clean Short-Haul Experimental Engine, developed by General Electric (GE) under contract with NASA Lewis (23). The cowl defines the inner boundary of the fan air flowpath from the fan frame to the engine core nozzle. The cowl was autoclave fabricated by GE from PMR-15 and Union Carbide's T300 graphite fabric. The cowl has a maximum diameter of about 91 cm and is primarily of honeycomb sandwich construction. Hexcel's HRH327 fiberglass polyimide honeycomb was used as the core material. The honeycomb core was bonded to the inner surface of the premolded outer skin with duPont's NR150B2G adhesive. The inner skin was then co-cured and bonded with NR150B2G to the core surface of the honeycomb core/outer skin assembly. Complete details about the cowl fabrication process are given in reference 24. The cowl was installed on the QCSEE engine and did not exhibit any degradation after more than 300 hours of ground engine testing. The maximum temperature experienced by the cowl during testing was 260°C (25). The successful autoclave fabrication and ground engine testing of the QCSEE inner cowl established the feasibility of using PMR-15 composite materials for large engine static structures.

Figure 5. - Graphite fiber/PMR-15 polyimide inner cowl installed on QCSEE engine.

Figure 6. - Graphite fiber/PMR-15 duct (75 cm diam. x 105 cm l. x 0.22 cm. wall thickness).

Under a jointly sponsored U.S. Navy/NASA Lewis program (NAS3-21854), GE is developing a T300 Graphite fabric/PMR-15 composite outer duct to replace the titanium duct presently used on the F404 engine for the U.S. Navy's F18 strike fighter. The titanium duct is a sophisticated part made by forming and machining titanium plates followed by chem milling to reduce weight. A preliminary cost-benefit study indicated that significant cost and weight savings (26) could be achieved by replacing the titanium duct with a composite duct. The F404 composite duct differs from the QCSEE inner cowl in several important aspects. The F404 duct is a monolithic composite structure, needs to withstand fairly high loads and, perhaps most importantly, the F404 duct is to be a production component and not a "one-of-a-kind" demonstration component. A full-scale composite duct (75 cm diameter by 105 cm length by 0.22 cm wall thickness) has been autoclave fabricated. The overall duct fabrication process consists of many operations. The sequence of the major operations is as follows: (1) autoclave fabrication of the composite shell, (2) ultrasonic inspection, (3) drilling of the buildups and (4) attachment of the split line stiffeners and titanium end-flanges. Figure 6 shows a photograph of the completed outer duct. The duct was installed on an F404 engine (Figure 7) and has successfully undergone more than 1000 hours of engine testing. The fully flight qualified, T300/PMR-15 composite outer duct entered into production during the first-half of 1985.

Figure 8 shows a full-scale composite forward inner duct fabricated by GE for their F110 engine. The approximate dimensions of the duct which was autoclave fabricated from T300 graphite fabric/PMR-15 are 102 cm diameter by 38 cm length by 0.15 cm wall thickness. Engine testing demonstrated that the

Figure 7. - Graphite fiber/PMR-15 outer duct installed on an F404 engine (composite duct located directly above carriage).

Figure 8. - Graphite fiber/PMR-15 F110 inner duct (diameter = 102 cm, length = 38 cm, and thickness = 0.15 cm.).

composite duct was fully functional and met engine performance requirements. The T300/PMR-15 composite inner duct is the current bill-of-materials for the F110 engine.

The current bill-of-materials inlet particle separator swirl frame on GE's T700 engine is an all metal part that involves machining, shape-forming, welding, and brazing operations. Design studies conducted under U.S. Army contract number DDAK51-79-C0018 indicated that the fabrication of a metal/composite swirl frame could result in a cost and weight savings of about 30 percent. Figure 9 shows a schematic diagram of a section of the metal/composite swirl frame that was fabricated from 410 stainless steel and various kinds of PMR-15 composite materials. The outer casing uses stainless steel in the flow path area to meet anti-icing temperature requirements and T300 and glass fabric/PMR-15 hybrid composite to meet structural requirements. The T300/glass hybrid composite was selected on the basis of both cost and structural considerations. An aluminum-coated glass fabric/PMR-15 composite material is utilized in the inner hub flowpath to meet heat transfer requirements for anti-icing. The glass fabric/PMR-15 composite utilized for the front-edge and front-inner surfaces was selected because of cost as well as temperature considerations. A full-scale (O.D. of about 51 cm) metal/composite swirl frame has been subjected to sand erosion and ice ball impact tests. The metal/composite swirl frame provided improved particle separation and successfully met the impact test requirements. Fabrication feasibility has been demonstrated, and if the metal/composite swirl frame successfully meets all of the performance requirements, the metal/composites swirl frame will be used on a growth version of the T700.

Figure 9. - Schematic section of the T700 PMR-15 composite swirl frame(O.D. \approx 51 cm.).

Figure 10 shows a photograph of a DC-9 aircraft. The inserts schematically depict the design of the presently used metal reverser stang fairing and a composite redesigned fairing developed by Douglas Aircraft Company under the NASA Lewis Engine Component Improvement Program (27). Studies had shown that a redesigned fairing provided an opportunity to reduce baseline drag and would result in reduced fuel consumption. The fairing serves as the aft enclosure for the thrust reverser actuator system on the nacelle of the JT8D engine and is subjected to a maximum exhaust temperature of 260°C during thrust reversal. A Kevlar fabric/PMR-15 composite fairing was autoclave fabricated and flight-tested. Compared to the metal component, the composite fairing resulted in a one-percent airplane drag reduction (1/2 percent had been anticipated) and a 40 percent reduction in component weight.

Figure 10. - Douglas DC-9 airplane. Inserts schematically show the current production metal fairing and the redesigned composite fairing.

The CASTS (Composites for Advanced Space Transportation Systems) program was undertaken by NASA Langley to develop graphite/polyimide composites for application to future aerospace vehicles. Potential applications of graphite/PMR polyimide composites on the shuttle orbiter are indicated in Figure 11. As part of the CASTS Program, Boeing Aerospace Company developed manufacturing processes for fabrication of graphite/PMR-15 structural elements and demonstrated their structural integrity at temperature up to 316°C (28). The structural elements consisted of flat panels, corrugated stiffeners, I-beams, hat stiffeners, honeycomb panels, and chopped fiber moldings. A section (76 cm wide x 203 cm long x 56 cm tapered to 15 cm thick) of a simulated shuttle orbiter aft body flap (full scale, 213 x 640 cm) was successfully fabricated. Thus, demonstrating that the manufacturing processes which were developed for structural elements could be adapted to large scale airframe hardware.

Figure 11. - Potential applications of graphite fiber/PMR-15 on shuttle orbiter.

Figure 12 shows a mercury ion thruster for an auxiliary propulsion system being built by Hughes Space and Communications Group under contract to NASA Lewis. The ion propulsion system is scheduled for launch and testing on a future space shuttle flight. The thruster is equipped with a glass fabric/PMR-15 composite beam shield to protect the solar arrays and sensitive

Figure 12. - Mercury ion thruster equipped with glass fabric/PMR-15 beam shield (shield diameter = 25 cm.).

instrumentation on the spacecraft from ion-beam damage. The composite shield (approximate dimensions: 25 cm diameter x 20 cm length x 0.1 cm thickness) was selected over tantalum and titanium because of weight and structural considerations. The feasibility of using a glass fabric/PMR-15 composite shield was demonstrated by in-house fabrication and testing of full-scale beam shields.

Concluding Remarks

The in situ polymerization of monomer reactants (PMR) approach has been demonstrated to be a powerful approach for solving many of the processing difficulties associated with the use of high-temperature resistant polymers as matrix resins in high performance composites. PMR-15, the PMR polyimide discovered in the early seventies, provides the best overall balance of processing characteristics and elevated temperature properties. The excellent properties and commercial availability of composite materials based on PMR-15 have led to their acceptance as viable engineering materials. PMR-15 composites are currently being used to produce a variety of high quality structural components. Significantly increased use of these materials is anticipated in the future.

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